

Cebu Motor Hailing Apps: User Insights Toward Better Services And Usability

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Abstract

This study employs a mixed-method through combining sentiment analysis with a survey questionnaire administered to over a hundred Cebuano motor-hailing app users to examine the insights of four major platforms: Angkas, Maxim, Move It, and JoyRide. Anchored on the Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning Model, SERVQUAL Model, Uses and Gratifications Theory, and the Technology Acceptance Model, the study identifies customer personas and explores user preferences, sentiments, motivations, challenges, and favored features. Findings reveal four distinct user personas such as Angkas as Practical Commuter, Budget Saver for Maxim, Versatile User for Move It, and Routine Commuter for JoyRide. Despite the contradictory experiences of users, Move It remains to be a strongly preferred choice due to its features, Angkas users generally have a positive view of the app, considering it a preferred option for their transportation needs, Maxim solves the everyday transportation needs of the users making it a preferred choice, and due to loyalty and habitual preference to other motor-hailing apps, JoyRide remains not preferred by Cebuano users. Analysis shows Angkas receives generally positive feedback, Maxim and JoyRide are viewed neutrally, while Move It receives mostly negative sentiment. Move It is strongly preferred while Angkas and Maxim are preferred while JoyRide is not preferred. Cebuanos primarily use Angkas, Maxim, and Move It for their accessibility, affordability, routine convenience, and positive driver interactions. While most users reported minimal challenges, notable issues include limited driver availability during peak hours, bad weather or nighttime, rude drivers, and delayed booking confirmations. Key features enjoyed across all platforms are convenience, time efficiency, affordable pricing, and safety. The study confirms that most Cebuanos use motor-hailing apps out of urgency and practicality. It is recommended that motor-hailing apps provide consistent updates based on user experiences, enhance technical features particularly real-time location tracking and localize marketing campaigns to boost app usability. Specific strategies include improving the user interface for Move It to streamline booking and navigation, implementing localized driver training programs for JoyRide to enhance customer service and safety, and introducing loyalty or rewards programs for Maxim to encourage user retention and frequent usage.

Keywords: Cebu, Commute, Marketing, Motor-hailing Apps, Traffic.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In many developing countries, traditional public transportation services struggle to meet the increasing demands of growing populations. Due to their accessibility, paratransit and car/van pools continue to be well-liked by regular commuters in developing nations. For short-distance transport, paratransit services, like Philippines' Jeepney or Jeep, and three-wheelers, like Thailand's Tuk Tuk, operate with more flexibility between origin and destination. Three-

wheeler paratransit is an often-offered flexible service in rural areas of developing countries; however, it is sometimes expensive and in short supply (Anburuvel et al.).

Alternatively, ride-hailing applications have significantly transformed public transportation systems (Giddy). These applications offer more convenience and affordability in transportation options, making them a popular choice among commuters in densely populated areas. However, despite their advantages, ride-hailing services encounter several challenges, including safety concerns, fare regulations, and the need for improved social protection measures (Tirachi).

The same problem is also experienced in Lahore, Pakistan, where public transportation remains inadequate. Based on an analysis of 531 survey responses, the most critical factors influencing customer satisfaction include comfort, convenience, privacy and security, fare systems, and social protection. The findings indicate a generally positive assessment of ride-hailing services, with a strong correlation between user satisfaction and future usage preferences. Notably, 81.73% of respondents were male, and 55.74% were under the age of 30, suggesting a user base with greater exposure to technology. The study highlights the importance of strengthening regulatory frameworks to enhance safety and social protection, which could further improve commuter satisfaction and increase service utilization. Moreover, the results underscore the potential of ride-hailing services as sustainable alternatives in the development of urban transportation systems (Ali et al.).

Ride-hailing applications such as Grab, All Taxi Thai, Line Taxi, and Taxi OK are widely used in Bangkok, Thailand, as alternative modes of transportation. Commuters frequently rely on these services for daily travel to work, school, shopping malls, and markets, particularly to avoid the inconvenience of traditional public transportation during peak hours. These applications cater to customer preferences by introducing cleaner vehicles, training drivers to be more courteous, and enhancing complaint management through efficient support systems. Additionally, GPS technology ensures accurate tracking and fair pricing, while loyalty programs and promotional offers help retain users. However, gaps remain in responsiveness and empathy, indicating areas for further improvement (Ruamchart).

Similarly, transportation shortages pose a significant challenge in Olongapo City, where tricycles, pedicabs, and jeepneys are often improperly parked, contributing to traffic congestion. Ride-hailing services such as Grab and Angkas serve as alternative transportation options, primarily for commuting to work, school, and commercial areas. These services provide faster and more efficient travel; however, concerns regarding pricing and accessibility persist. Many residents continue to prefer traditional transportation methods, such as jeepneys and tricycles, due to their familiarity and affordability (Cueto et al.).

Despite this, the emergence of motor-hailing applications in the Philippines has become an essential alternative to traditional public transportation, particularly in urban cities like Cebu. Four major apps widely used in the country are Angkas, which pioneered motorcycle taxis with several promos and a strong safety focus (Cebu Insights); Maxim, known for offering affordable taxis and motorcycles (Sunstar Publishing Inc., 2024); Move It, which operates under Grab's technology platform to offer cost-effective motorcycle rides; and JoyRide, which provides a wide range of services, such as motorcycle taxis, car, and tricycle options (Mrgx). These apps supply a more efficient and affordable travel option, particularly in congested areas, making them popular choices for commuters seeking alternatives to traditional public transport in rapidly growing urban centers (Mrgx).

Although previous studies have explored various aspects of ride-hailing applications, there remains an empirical gap in understanding their utilization in Cebu. Specifically, there is a need for further research into customer personas, their preferences, sentiments toward the apps, their underlying reasons for utilization, encountered challenges, and enjoyed features.

This study is significant as it sheds light on the usage of motor hailing applications in Cebu, particularly Angkas, Maxim, Move It, and JoyRide. By analyzing the local commuter landscape and comparing user experiences among the various platforms, the findings can aid transport service providers in providing efficient mobility solutions.

Moreover, this study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for Sustainable Cities and Communities, Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, and Decent Work and Economic Growth. The study aims to improve app features, address user concerns, and promote inclusivity within this transportation sector (THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development). It promotes Sustainable Cities as it examines how motor hailing apps provide accessible, efficient, and inclusive transport solutions for local commuters. It also supports Innovation and Infrastructure by highlighting how digital platforms evolve in response to user needs and technological trends. Furthermore, the study contributes to Decent Work and Economic Growth by recognizing the role of motor hailing services in generating employment and upholding for better working conditions among riders and platform workers.

The study assumes that the Cebuanos utilize the motor hailing apps out of urgency. The study also investigates the insights of motor hailing applications in Cebu by identifying the customer personas of four major platforms: Angkas, Maxim, Move It, and JoyRide, along with examining user preferences, sentiments toward the apps, their underlying reasons for utilization, encountered challenges, and enjoyed features.

The theories that the study is anchored to the study are Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP) Model by Philip Kotler, SERVQUAL Model by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) by Katz and Blumler, and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Fred Davis.

The first theory, the STP Model, introduced by Philip Kotler in 1969, is a consumer-focused marketing framework comprising three steps: segmenting, targeting, and positioning. This approach enables marketers to divide a broad market into smaller segments, select the most appropriate ones, and position offerings to meet the unique needs of those segments (Segmenting, Targeting and Positioning (STP) Framework in Marketing). STP is used in this study to examine the unique customer personas of JoyRide, Maxim, Move It, and Angkas. It will assist in determining which commuter demographics each app targets and how these platforms build themselves up to meet user needs in the context of urban transportation in Cebu.

The SERVQUAL Model by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry developed in 1988 is the second theory in this study, which is a multidimensional framework used to measure service quality by assessing the gap between customer expectations and their perceptions of the actual service received (Masud). In this study, customer preferences and sentiments for the four major motor-hailing apps in Cebu are assessed using the SERVQUAL Model. Through an analysis of these characteristics, the study seeks to pinpoint areas in which these applications either meet or surpass user expectations.

The third theory is Katz and Blumler's Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), conceived in the 1940s, which posits that individuals actively seek out media to satisfy specific needs and desires, viewing users as engaged and intentional in their media consumption choices (Vinney).

Whether it is speed, convenience of booking, cost savings, or safety, UGT assists in this study by determining the fundamental reasons behind commuters' usage of motor-hailing apps as well as the features they find most appealing. It contributes to a better understanding of app loyalty by illuminating user motivation and satisfaction.

Lastly, the study uses Fred Davis' Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed in 1989, which explores how individuals come to accept and use technology. It identifies two main factors that influence technology acceptance: perceived usefulness (PU), or the belief that using a system will enhance performance, and perceived ease of use (PEOU), or the belief that using the system will require minimal effort (Marikyan & Papagiannidis). In the context of this study, TAM helps explain resistance or inclination toward particular motor hailing apps by examining how users see the features, design, and accessibility of each app, offering suggestions for enhancing user experience and adoption.

In summary, the integration of the STP Model, SERVQUAL Model, Uses and Gratifications Theory, and Technology Acceptance Model presents a thorough theoretical and conceptual framework for comprehending the dynamics of motor-hailing app usage in Cebu. Using these theories, a strategic plan of action can be developed to meet customer demands, enhance user experience, and improve service quality in Cebu's motor hailing app industry.

2.0 METHODS

The study uses a mixed method design, which is a framework that merges both quantitative and qualitative designs, providing a deeper understanding providing a complement of the accuracy of quantitative methods and the in-depth exploration of the qualitative method (George). This research design aids on analyzing the customer personas of the four major motor hailing apps in Cebu, along with the user preferences, sentiments toward the apps, their underlying reasons for utilization, encountered challenges, and enjoyed features.

Furthermore, the research environment of the study is in Cebu, which is a major island in Central Visayas, Philippines, known for its vibrant culture, history, and city life (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica). Cebu is chosen as the research environment as it is one of the key areas where motor hailing apps such as Angkas, Maxim, Move It, and JoyRide are actively operating, proving there is a growing demand for alternative transportation options amid increasing traffic congestion (Mrgx). Moreover, the study gathered data from a total of 110 respondents who were selected using a random sampling approach. Only individuals who had used any of the motor hailing apps included in the study are qualified as respondents.

To collect the data, survey type and open-ended questionnaires are used as instrumentations. The survey questionnaire is designed to gather quantifiable data on respondents' demographics, usage, and preferences with motor hailing apps, while the open-ended questionnaire aims to capture more detailed, qualitative insights on their sentiments toward the apps, underlying reasons for utilization, experienced challenges, and enjoyed features. Additionally, thematic analysis, sentiment analysis, and discourse analysis are employed in this study to interpret both quantitative and qualitative data. Thematic analysis is applied to identify common patterns and insights in the customer persona and customer preference responses. Sentiment analysis is employed to assess the emotional tone of respondents' feedback toward each app, categorizing them into positive, negative, or neutral sentiments. Lastly, discourse analysis is utilized to examine open-ended responses related to the underlying reasons for app utilization, encountered challenges, and enjoyed features.

The study uses Sentiment Analysis test available on BoardFlare powered by Azure AI Language and trained on Twitter messages to automatically categorize public opinions about these services as positive, negative, or neutral. The sentiment analysis was conducted using the Azure AI Language Sentiment Analysis API (version 3.1), which utilizes a pre-trained convolutional neural network (CNN) model. To ensure high data integrity, a confidence score threshold of 0.75 was established; any sentiment labels falling below this probability were manually reviewed for context or categorized as neutral. In handling 'neutral' sentiments, the study followed the consensus model where neutral scores (typically ranging between 0.45 and 0.55 in Azure's normalized output) were excluded from the final polarity calculation to prevent dilution of the distinct positive and negative sentiment trends, ensuring a clearer representation of active user satisfaction. By processing reviews from both Google Play store and Apple App Store this Azure AI Language-driven, Twitter-based sentiment model, the study is able to quantify overall rider and driver satisfaction, identify emerging issues and observe shifts in user attitudes over time. This methodology provides scalable, data-driven insights based on real-time feedback rather than relying solely on manual surveys or interviews.

Statements are coded for their confidentiality. Respondents from the survey are labeled as R1-110 while sentiments from users are labeled as A1-200 for Angkas users, M1-200 for Maxim, MI1-200 for Move It users, and lastly, J1-200 for JoyRide users.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the results and discussion following the assumption that the Cebuanos utilize the motor hailing apps out of urgency. This also identifies the customer personas of four major platforms: Angkas, Maxim, Move It, and JoyRide, along with examining user preferences, sentiments toward the apps, their underlying reasons for utilization, encountered challenges, and enjoyed features.

User Persona Analysis

This section discusses the persona of the users of the four motor-hailing apps in Cebu.

Table 1. User Persona

Motor-hailing Apps	Persona Name	Persona Description
Angkas	Practical Commuter	A Gen Z student who commutes twice a week in the morning, pays in cash, and prefers reliable transport for school and quick errands.
Maxim	Budget Saver	A young professional who travels a few times a month in the morning, pays in cash, and seeks the most affordable option for school and leisure.
Move It	Versatile User	A multitasking young professional who commutes several times a week in the afternoon, pays via cash or e-wallet, and uses transport for errands, side gigs, and deliveries.

JoyRide	Routine Commuter	A Gen Z student who commutes twice a day for school, switching between cash and e-wallet for consistent, dependable rides.
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Table 1 presents the personas where the user persona name of Angkas is “Practical Commuter,” describing it as a Gen Z student commuting twice weekly in the morning, pays in cash, and prefers trustworthy rides for school and errands. Meanwhile, Maxim’s persona name is “Budget Saver,” detailed as a young professional commuting a few times monthly in the morning, pays in cash, and seeks the cheapest option for a motor hailing ride. Moreover, Move It is described as a busy young professional who commutes several afternoons weekly, pays through cash or e-wallet, and uses rides for errands, gigs, and deliveries, which earned it the name “Versatile User.” Lastly, JoyRide is the “Routine Commuter,” labeled as a Gen Z student who commutes twice daily for school, switches between cash and e-wallet for reliable rides.

The Angkas user persona, referred to as the “Practical Commuter,” represents a Gen Z student who commutes twice a week in the morning, pays in cash, and prefers reliable transport for school and quick errands. This persona aligns with more general trends of student mobility in Philippines cities, where commuter behavior is influenced by time constraints and traffic congestions. In the sense of brand awareness, Angkas is the most well-known amongst many Filipino college students who rely on motor hailing services to avoid unpredictability of public transportation, especially during morning hours when being on time for classes is essential (Manaois et al.).

In terms of payment, this persona’s preference for cash also reflects common patterns. Due in large part to its accessibility and usability, cash continues to be the most preferred payment method for many young commuters in the Philippines, despite the growing popularity of digital wallets (Manaois et al.). Students who may not have completely embraced financial technologies or who would rather not depend on them for regular, small payments will find this to be particularly pertinent. Moreover, students’ reliance on their parents for financial support renders it challenging for them to use mobile banking, and as a result, cash payment methods are more preferable to them.

Furthermore, motorcycles are popular in most Southeast Asian cities because of their speed and ease in traffic, especially where public transit systems are weak. Gen Zs opt for affordable but less eco-friendly options like motor hailing rides due to their reliability and safety concerns with public transport (Fisu et al.). In Cebu, this clarifies why Angkas attracts Gen Z commuters, as it offers greater reliability and convenience compared to buses or jeepneys, aligning with the Gen Z commuter's demand for a trustworthy, adaptable mode of transportation.

The Practical Commuter persona of Angkas reflects the brand’s strategic use of the Segmenting, Targeting, Position (STP) Model by Philip Kotler, which aims to identify specific customer groups (segmentation), determine which groups to serve (targeting), and create a differentiated brand image that appeals to the chosen segment (positioning). By segmenting the market through demographics (youth), behavioral traits (commuting frequency), and psychographics (preference for convenience and speed), Angkas strategically targets Gen Z, a digitally fluent and trend-sensitive audience.

In addition, memes have a substantial impact on Gen Z participation by promoting social contact and offering enjoyment (Bowo et al.). Angkas' meme-driven marketing, distinguished by witty posts and culturally relevant content, also aligns with the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) by Katz and Blumler. UGT posits that users actively choose media that satisfies their psychological and social needs. In this case, Gen Z users are drawn to Angkas content not only for transportation information but for entertainment, identity expression, and social interaction. The brand's humorous and shareable posts cater to Gen Z's desire for online engagement and self-representation, allowing Angkas to build cultural relevance and emotional resonance with its audience. By doing so, Angkas does not simply inform—it embeds itself into the everyday digital rituals of young commuters.

In terms of technology adoption, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) further explains why this segment chooses Angkas. While digital wallets are on the rise, many students still pay in cash, suggesting that ease of use and perceived usefulness remain central to their choice of service. Despite the app's digital payment capabilities, users value simplicity and dependability over complete financial technology tool integration. These actions suggest that perceived utility (getting to class on time, avoiding traffic) and reported ease of use (the app's user-friendly interface, the ability to swiftly book a ride) are important factors in their decision to keep using Angkas. This supports the notion that, in actual commuting situations, user choices are dominated by functionality and dependability, even when digital sophistication is important.

Furthermore, Angkas' brand positioning and primary value proposition as a dependable and effective substitute for public transportation are reinforced by the tagline “Beat the Traffic.” It conveys dependability and speed, qualities that Gen Z students really respect as they navigate Cebu's urban challenges.

Overall, the Practical Commuter persona shows how Angkas effectively presents itself as a trustworthy and user-friendly motor hailing ride choice by combining ease of use, cultural relevance, and functionality—satisfying Gen Z's demand for quick, dependable, and socially engaging transportation.

On the other hand, Maxim's user persona, referred to as the “Budget Saver,” is a young professional who commutes a few times a month, typically in the mornings, pays in cash, and prioritizes low-cost transportation for both school and leisure. Due to their low budget and infrequent travel requirements, this user is particularly price-sensitive and seeks for the most economical choice.

This user persona's behavior mirrors broader patterns in Filipino urban mobility, where younger, budget-conscious individuals prefer services that offer both affordability and reliability. Research conducted in Cebu indicates that a significant portion of commuters are young individuals aged 13 to 30 years, with 46% being workers who shuttle daily from home to their offices or factories. The majority of travelers cited work-related and school-related reasons for commuting, highlighting the essential nature of their travel needs (World Bank et al.).

Furthermore, a study conducted in Quezon City found that cost efficiency is a significant determinant of commuter satisfaction, with passengers valuing affordable prices and time-saving advantages (Galvez et al.). This aligns with Maxim's persona, who prefers low-cost transportation options. Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of service quality and safety, particularly among female commuters, suggesting that while affordability is crucial, service reliability and safety are also significant considerations (Galvez et al.).

However, concerns are raised about Maxim's dependability and adherence to legal requirements. In 2023, Maxim is designated as a "colorum" ride-hailing app by the Land Transportation Franchising and Regulatory Board (LTFRB), which means it operates without the required accreditation and oversight, raising concerns about safety, driver training, and customer service (Abadilla). In addition, there are reports of fraudulent activity on Maxim's platform, which has led the company to add new security measures to safeguard client data (Piquero). Despite ongoing concerns about the app's legality, safety, and service reliability, Maxim continues to be used by commuters who fall under the Budget Saver persona. For these users, the appeal of low-cost fares often outweighs the risks linked with the service quality and regulatory compliance.

Moreover, Maxim's persona's preference for cash payment further reinforces the theme of cost-consciousness. Despite the growing popularity of digital payment methods, cash remains the predominant choice for many Filipino commuters, particularly among lower-income groups. Cash is favored due to its simplicity, ease of access, and avoidance of transaction fees often associated with digital payments (Massally et al.). This choice is proven applicable to the Budget Saver, who prefers simple transactions over the potential difficulties that come with digital wallets.

The app's strategic application of the STP (Segmenting, Targeting, Positioning) Model is demonstrated by Maxim's Budget Saver persona. Maxim targets users who value affordability over service assurances by segmenting their market psychographically (price-sensitive commuters), behaviorally (regular users), and demographically (young professionals). It markets itself as an inexpensive substitute for more expensive and regulated motor-hailing applications, aiming to attract users on a tight budget who commute for both work and leisure. Despite not having regulatory approval, this positioning makes it appealing to commuters with a low income.

In line with the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), Budget Savers use Maxim mostly for functional gratifications, such as affordability and usefulness for basic transportation needs. The instant, useful advantage of inexpensive rides is what these users appreciate most, not brand loyalty or improved app capabilities. This behavior exemplifies how financial necessity frequently takes precedence over enjoyments like amusement, social interaction, or security. Maxim illustrates a perceived trade-off between price and service quality when analyzed using the SERVQUAL model. Although the cheap cost is a selling element, users have expressed worries about safety, legality, and app dependability, particularly when authorities designated Maxim a "colorum" service. Due to cost constraints, the Budget Saver accepts a service quality gap that is shown by the absence of certainty in the reliability, responsiveness, and assurance dimensions.

The continued preference for Maxim despite its 'colorum' status presents significant ethical and policy implications. From a safety perspective, users who prioritize affordability (the 'Budget Saver' persona) essentially trade-off formal regulatory protections and insurance guarantees for lower fares. This highlights a 'governance gap' where the state's inability to provide affordable, legal transport alternatives drives the public toward unauthorized services. For policymakers, this suggests that enforcement alone is insufficient; there is a critical need to streamline the accreditation process for motor-hailing apps to ensure that price-sensitive commuters are not forced to choose between financial practicality and personal safety.

Based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the persona's inclination for cash over digital payments indicates a lack of confidence in or perception of the usability of digital

financial tools. These users might not find digital wallets handy or helpful enough to change their payment habits, even when the app is available on smartphones. They choose cash instead because it is straightforward and predictable, which highlights the obstacles to this segment's use of technology for financial transactions.

Ultimately, the Budget Saver persona demonstrates how Maxim draws in cost-conscious young professionals who value simplicity and affordability over legal compliance and service dependability.

Meanwhile, Move It's user persona, represented by the name "Versatile User," is a multitasking young professional who commutes several times weekly in the afternoon, pays through cash and e-wallet, and utilizes transport for errands, side gigs, and deliveries. This is indicative of an increasingly prevalent pattern of behavior among urban commuters whose mobility requirements go beyond everyday commuting to include a range of lifestyle demands.

In a study on post-pandemic mobility shifts in Metro Cebu, it is noted that young professionals are increasingly making short, purpose-driven journeys. Apart from work-related commuting, respondents have indicated a wider range of travel objectives, such as personal tasks and errands (Mayo et al.). This change reinforces the notion that modern urban users favor mobility platforms that provide flexibility in usage scenarios—services that are not just available but also adaptable to a variety of intersecting demands in a single day.

Users' dependence on applications like Move It for logistical convenience is reflected in the inclusion of deliveries in this persona's daily routine. In order to support their multitasking lifestyle, Versatile Users utilize the platform to deliver meals, packages, or other products rather than doing the delivery work themselves. This larger trend is demonstrated by the Jojo Crowdfunding App's entry into Pampanga, where users' growing need for instant, app-based solutions to meet daily logistics demands led to a spike in demand for flexible delivery services (Punto! Central Luzon).

Furthermore, Move It's persona's dual payment behavior, which alternates between cash and e-wallets, reflects the digital payment ecosystem's current transitory phase in the Philippines. Considering e-wallets are convenient and becoming more common in cities, younger commuters are using them frequently (Belmonte et al.). Similar to Angkas' feature, Move It's ability to automatically deduct payment from the user's e-wallet once arrived at the destination makes it more convenient compared to manually transferring money from one e-wallet to another. However, cash is still a common choice because of inconsistent internet connectivity, mistrust of digital systems, or driver preference. Studies on Southeast Asian ride-hailing users reveal that cash usage continues even in highly urbanized regions because of specific factors and service limitations, demonstrating that this flexible payment behavior is not exclusive to the Philippines (Le & Hilton).

The "Versatile User" persona aligns with Philip Kotler's STP Model, demonstrating how Move It segments, targets, and positions itself in a competitive market. With adaptable features that meet their various needs, Move It successfully divides up a population of urban multitaskers.

The app is positioned as a multipurpose platform rather than merely a commuting solution due to its capacity to handle various travel objectives, such as personal transportation and on-demand delivery services. This is particularly apparent with the brand's Parcel Delivery Service, which enables customers to send items inside Metro Manila, Metro Cebu, and Cagayan de Oro during off-peak hours. This service, which is available through the app, provides users with ease, real-time tracking, and guaranteed pricing, enabling them to handle their logistics and

mobility requirements in a single ecosystem (Grab Editorial). This kind of integration enhances Move It's market position as a useful, versatile solution by appealing to users with busy schedules and numerous obligations.

From the perspective of the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), users consciously choose Move It due to its ability to satisfy their demands for task integration, control, and efficiency. More than just a means of transportation, the app turns into a digital tool that boosts efficiency and simplifies daily tasks. In addition to reflecting the app's ability to adjust to users' situational preferences and infrastructural constraints, the dual-payment option (cash and e-wallets) further enhances its allure for practical, convenience-driven individuals (Belmonte et al.; Le & Hilton).

With features that are flexible and payment alternatives that allow for multitasking, Move It's Versatile User persona reflects the demand for flexibility of modern urban commuters, who employ the app for errands and deliveries alongside transportation.

Even with a small sample size—only five out of 110 respondents claimed they utilized JoyRide—this subset provides valuable qualitative information about the brand's user base. Despite that none of the respondents chose JoyRide as their preferred motor-hailing app, the “Routine Commuter” profile is created based on the constant characteristics found in their responses. This user persona is a representation of a Gen Z student that uses JoyRide to get reliable, consistent rides, commutes twice daily for school, and alternates between paying with cash and an e-wallet.

The decision of developing a user persona from such a small sample is consistent with well-established qualitative research methodologies that value specificity above generality. In qualitative research, small samples can still be adequate to uncover significant patterns and reach close to code saturation, particularly when the data is thematically coherent and targeted (Squire et al.).

Similar to the other users of motor hailing apps, JoyRide users reflect broader behavior patterns among urban commuters in the Philippines. Move It's Versatile User, who also exhibits a flexible payment preference, is mirrored in JoyRide's Routine Commuter's alternating use of cash and e-wallets. This reflects the current payment situation in the Philippines, where cash is still used because of infrastructural constraints, a lack of trust in digital systems, or driver-specific preferences, despite e-wallets becoming growing in popularity among younger, urban users for their convenience (Belmonte et al.; Le & Hilton). This dual-payment pattern demonstrates how Gen Z commuters navigate service limitations while progressively embracing digital financial practices, demonstrating a flexible attitude to transportation.

Furthermore, a typical response to the inadequacies of Philippine public transportation is reflected in the JoyRide persona's need for reliable and stable rides. Traffic congestion, lengthy commutes, and safety concerns are identified as the main stressors that impact daily routines and academic focus in research on Manila students' commutes. Accordingly, students set a high priority on transportation options that guarantee timeliness and minimize waiting (Morales et al.).

Although JoyRide might not be the most popular motor-hailing app in Cebu, its capacity to offer solid substitutes for quick, everyday commutes, particularly in cities, satisfies students' demands for dependable mobility options. In this way, even the respondents' minimal

utilization of JoyRide is in line with the priorities of commuters as perceived by other platforms.

Applying the Uses and Gratifications Theory, JoyRide users—especially Gen Z students—consciously select the app to meet functional needs, such as consistency, dependability, and managing daily routines. By guaranteeing reliable and efficient transportation, their usage of JoyRide demonstrates deliberate behavior meant to reduce academic stress. These users find satisfaction in its usefulness, which makes it a tool for keeping their balance between school and life organized.

Complementing this, the SERVQUAL model clarifies how important responsiveness and dependability are to JoyRide users. The Routine Commuter appreciates JoyRide's contribution to lowering commute-related uncertainty in an environment where public transit is frequently unreliable. In addition to pointing to tangibles and assurance dimensions, the dual-payment behavior also shows that users value options that support both traditional accessibility and digital convenience, particularly in situations where service limits occur. JoyRide may not be the most popular app, but its perceived service quality in certain areas, such as dependability, makes it a reliable substitute for routine users.

JoyRide is a reliable choice for Gen Z students looking for reliable, stress-free transportation options for their everyday routines, although its utilization among respondents in Cebu is minimal.

In summary, the user personas for each of the motor hailing apps are Practical Commuter for Angkas, Budget Saver for Maxim, Versatile User for Move It, and Routine Commuter for JoyRide, which provide an extensive understanding of the unique behaviors, motivations, and preferences that define their respective user groups.

User Preference Analysis

This section discusses the customer preferences of Cebuanos between the four motor-hailing apps.

Table 2. Customer Preference

Motor-hailing Apps	Level of Preference	Description
Move It	4.04	Strongly Preferred
Angkas	3.62	Preferred
Maxim	3.69	Preferred
JoyRide	2.44	Not Preferred

1.0 - 1.9 = Strongly Not Preferred

2.0 - 2.9 = Not Preferred

3.0 - 3.9 = Preferred

4.0 - 5.0 = Strongly Preferred

Table 2 presents the customer preference where Move It claims the highest user preference with a score of 4.04, categorizing it as strongly preferred. Followed by Maxim with 3.69 and Angkas with 3.62 in the preferred category, while JoyRide ranks the lowest with a score of 2.44, indicating it as not preferred. These findings suggest that Move It leads in user satisfaction, while JoyRide demonstrates a need for improvement to compete effectively with its competitors

Move It

Based on the data presented in Table 2, Move It received a 4.03 score that makes it the strongly preferred motor hailing app. Users generally view Move It as the top-performing app for both user rating and overall performance, showing their satisfaction towards Move It compared to the other apps.

One of the few reasons for preference is its affordability. R59 said “Move it gets a 5 because I love its service especially when they provide hair net for the helmet and it is also on the cheaper side which is perfect for students like me.”

Another reason is its safety. According to Insurance Asia, AXA Philippines, a notable insurance company, partners with Grab and Move It. The insurance benefits include coverage for life, accidents, disabilities, and terminal illnesses. This move is part of AXA’s global inclusive insurance program, AXA EssentiALL, which delivers affordable, customized insurance for underserved communities. This new offering complements the existing insurance drivers and riders already receive during bookings or deliveries (“AXA Philippines Partners with Grab, MOVE IT on Gig Insurance”).

Ride-hailing services have quickly grown in the Philippines, providing commuters with easy, safe, and budget-friendly travel options. These platforms cater to a wide range of needs, from car rides to motorcycle taxis and delivery services (Kapil and Kapil).

R12 shared that:

“I got lost on the way to my new school and this app helped me a lot. The driver was very enthusiastic and friendly, without making it awkward or uncomfy. He seemed to enjoy what he was doing, as he was promoting the app. Ana siya nga naa daw insurance ang trip so safety rajud. He even gave me vouchers” (“I got lost on the way to my new school, and this app helped me a lot. The driver was very enthusiastic and friendly, without making it awkward or uncomfortable. He seemed to enjoy what he was doing, as he was promoting the app. He said that the trip comes with insurance, so it's really safe. He even gave me vouchers.”

This feedback highlighted that Move It is indeed strongly preferred because of its convenience, accessibility and affordability.

In spite of the numbers dictating the strong preference to Move It, surveys and sentiments also show a negative experience mentioning that riders are reckless.

R109 complains “Move-it ang pinaka kamote mo drive gyud. Ambot nalang gyud. Usahay bisag asa mo lusot.” (“Move It has the most reckless drivers. Sometimes, they slip through almost anywhere.”)

This observed contradiction—where Move It maintains a high preference score (4.04) despite a negative sentiment score (-0.40)—can be theoretically explained through the concept of 'forced preference' driven by economic utility over service quality. While qualitative feedback highlights dissatisfaction with driver behavior, the quantitative data suggests that users prioritize the platform’s aggressive voucher system and lower price points, which reduce the 'perceived sacrifice' in the SERVQUAL model. Consequently, users exhibit a pragmatic loyalty; they continue to utilize and prefer the service not because of emotional satisfaction, but because the economic benefits and the necessity for urgent mobility in Cebu's traffic outweigh the negative experiential aspects

Although the Philippines is still a developing country, many Filipinos continue to use and download Move It despite negative experiences, as they often have no other choice and need to reach their destinations as quickly as possible. Its convenience, accessibility, and affordability leave users with limited alternatives.

Overall, despite the contradictory experiences of users, Move It remains to be a strongly preferred choice due to its features.

Angkas

As shown in table 2, Angkas earned a score of 3.62 which shows that it is also a preferred choice among motor-hailing app users. This suggests that users generally view the app positively, finding it dependable and satisfactory due to factors like rider availability, ease of use, and brand familiarity.

Under the lens of the Uses and Gratifications Theory, which emphasizes how individuals actively seek out media and technologies to satisfy specific needs. The preference for Angkas can be attributed to how it meets users' personal, functional, and emotional needs (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch).

R94 shared "I strongly prefer Angkas, not only because it's safe, but also because their pricing is student-friendly. They offer promos that I really love. And I also like the color of Angkas. it feels safe, friendly, and welcoming."

This statement shows both functional gratifications (affordability and safety) and affective gratifications (emotional connection to branding).

R109 mentioned "Angkas is really the best when it comes to their services. They have insurance, complete gear, good helmets, and even provide raincoats for back riders."

The statement from R109 emphasizes how Angkas meet users' need for safety and convenience, particularly during unpredictable weather conditions. Filipino commuters tend to prefer motorcycle-hailing services that offer safety assurances and practical add-ons, especially in the rainy season (Latonero et al.).

During the rainy season, many users opt for Angkas because it equips its drivers with rain gear for both riders and passengers. This safety-first approach—providing raincoats, helmets, and insurance—mitigates the discomfort and risk of riding in bad weather, making it a reliable choice.

As one of the first motorcycle-hailing apps in the Philippines, Angkas benefits from strong brand recognition. Familiarity fosters trust—users feel safer with a brand they've known longer, particularly when it comes to transportation and safety. This trust is reinforced by its professional branding and community presence, making it the go-to option for many.

Overall, Angkas users generally have a positive view of the app, considering it a preferred option for their transportation needs.

Maxim

Maxim emerges as one of the most preferred by Filipino commuters not just for its widespread usage, but for the consistent satisfaction it delivers. More than half of the respondents rate Maxim 4 or 5, indicating high satisfaction levels. In terms of preference, Maxim achieves a mean score of 3.69, placing it in the preferred category.

With over 10 million downloads on Google Play and a consistent ranking among top travel apps on the Apple App Store, Maxim shows strong nationwide usage. These figures confirm that its appeal goes beyond our respondents, it's a trusted choice for many Filipinos looking for affordable and reliable rides.

The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), audiences actively select media or services that meet their specific needs. For many users, Maxim meets functional gratifications, especially Budget Savers, who prioritize affordability, accessibility, and efficiency.

As R05 notes, Maxim offers "one-tap convenience, meets all needs, and good customer service with chatty, friendly drivers." This feedback highlights how Maxim addresses practical needs not through brand attachment but by consistently delivering inexpensive and reliable rides. Maxim proves that success in the motor-hailing industry does not always depend on flashy branding or advanced features but on fulfilling real, everyday needs. With a solid user base, high satisfaction scores, strong app performance, and clear alignment with users' practical motivations, Maxim remains a top choice for value-driven Filipino commuters. All in all, Maxim solves the everyday transportation needs of the users making it a preferred choice.

JoyRide

Based on the results presented in Table 2, JoyRide received an average preference rating of 2.44, categorizing it as not preferred among Cebuano users. It scored the lowest among the four motor-hailing apps analyzed, with zero respondents identifying it as their most used platform. Respondents shared that although JoyRide is affordable, it is rarely used due to limited visibility and service availability.

R02 stated, "Okay lang, affordable rasad sya pero rare kaayo nako nga magamit since mas naanad kos Maxim and Move It" (It's okay since it is affordable and I rarely use it since I am used to using Maxim and Move It), pointing to user loyalty and habitual use of other apps.

R03 also mentioned a "long waiting period," highlighting possible service inefficiencies that discourage repeat use.

Recent studies affirm that consumers engage more with transport platforms that meet their specific needs, such as convenience, responsiveness, and safety (Caliman & Teixeira; Lim et al.). These factors align with the modern understanding of Uses and Gratifications Theory, which has been revisited in digital service contexts, emphasizing that users gravitate toward platforms that actively satisfy their personal motives (Alalwan, 2020; Whiting & Williams). In this case, JoyRide is overshadowed by apps like Move It and Maxim, which respondents described as more familiar, reliable, and consistent in service. Without significant improvements in brand presence, rider availability, and user trust, JoyRide risks remaining a back-up option than a preferred one.

Despite its launch in 2019 (Manahan), JoyRide has not become Cebu's top motor taxi app because of Angkas' strong head start in 2017 (Mcosep, 2017), higher brand trust, and better local integration. JoyRide may remain underutilized unless it rebrands locally, improves driver availability, and offers better incentives for both riders and passengers.

In summary, due to loyalty and habitual preference to other motor-hailing apps, JoyRide remains not preferred by Cebuano users.

All in all, despite the contradictory experiences of users, Move It remains to be a strongly preferred choice due to its features, Angkas users generally have a positive view of the app, considering it a preferred option for their transportation needs, Maxim solves the everyday transportation needs of the users making it a preferred choice, and due to loyalty and habitual preference to other motor-hailing apps, JoyRide remains not preferred by Cebuano users.

Sentiment Analysis

This section discusses the sentiments of the motor-hailing app users. Due to limitations of the sentiments available via the Google Play Store and App Store, the sentiments come from varied places and are not necessarily from Cebu.

Table 3. Sentiments

Motor-hailing Apps	Score	Sentiment
Angkas	0.60	Positive
Maxim	0.14	Neutral
Move It	-0.40	Negative
JoyRide	0.08	Neutral

-1.00 and -0.60 = Very Negative

-0.61 and -0.20 = Negative

-0.21 and 0.20 = Neutral

0.21 and 0.60 = Positive

0.61 and 1.00 = Very Positive

As presented in Table 3, Angkas received a sentiment score of 0.60, indicating a positive public perception. In contrast, Maxim and JoyRide obtained sentiment scores of 0.14 and 0.08 respectively, both reflecting neutral sentiments. Move It, on the other hand, registered a sentiment score of -0.40, suggesting a negative public sentiment toward the service.

For Angkas, the score of 0.60 indicates a positive sentiment. Sentiments from Angkas include the themes of fast and convenient booking and/or transportation, user-friendly and easy-to-use interface, professional and respectful drivers, reliable, safe, and trustworthy service, affordable pricing, and loyalty and long-term satisfaction.

December 2016, Angkas is launched by Angeline Tham and her husband, George Royeca, who are driven by the need to address the worsening traffic congestion in the Philippines. After experiencing long travel hours herself, she recognized the potential of motorcycles as a faster, more efficient mode of transportation in urban areas. Drawing from her background in tech and logistics, Tham built Angkas not only to ease commuting struggles but also to provide safer, more professional job opportunities for motorcycle riders. Her vision combined mobility innovation with social impact, aiming to create both a transport solution and a sustainable livelihood platform (Co).

However, with their recent update in January of 2024, dubbed as the “Glow-App” referring to a slang term “glow up” signifying a noticeable improvement typically with physical appearances (“Glow-up”). The “Glow-App” introduced several new features aimed at improving the user experience for both riders and passengers. For riders, enhancements included an auto-accept feature for quicker bookings, improved tracking mechanisms, a better cashless option via the Angkas wallet, and destination matching. Passengers benefited from a more user-friendly interface, the addition of the Angkas Padala feature, GCash payment integration, and a saved places interface (INQUIRER.net).

One of the sentiments from an IOS user, A1 mentions that:

"Booking is a bit better and faster compared to the original app. I'm happy that I was able to use my Gcash and Maya accounts as card payments. Much more convenient to go cashless during these trips! HOWEVER, when I opt to manually pin the exact location for both my pickup and dropoff, the app pins a different area from the map..."

These improvements contribute to the positive sentiments of the users. Continuous updates driven by user feedback and market trends are essential for enhancing the app's features and performance. To maintain user engagement, it's important to consistently upgrade existing

features or introduce new ones, particularly in a digital landscape where numerous apps, websites, and media vie for users' attention (Oladele & Oladele).

One of the new features of the 2024 update is by providing users with faster and more convenient booking and/or transportation services. R15 mentions that "the new Angkas app is faster than the old one, i like that it doesn't give me a hard time looking for riders to fetch and take me to my destination..."

Additionally, the new update also offers a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface intended for their target audience who are the younger generations. Wilson emphasizes, usability hinges on making systems easy to learn, efficient to use, and satisfying for users. Younger users expect seamless digital experiences, so regular updates that improve learnability, reduce errors, and enhance satisfaction directly align with Nielsen's usability principles. By refining features based on user behavior and trends, Angkas ensures its app remains relevant and engaging in a competitive, attention-driven digital landscape.

A71 mentions that "The app's interface is user-friendly, making it easy to navigate and book a ride in just a few taps."

Moreover, users also notice that the drivers are professional and respectful. A12 Mentions that "My rider arrived on time, was professional, and ensured a safe and comfortable journey."

Users also observe the app's reliability, safety, and trustworthy service. A41 comments that "This commitment to safety is commendable and instills confidence in using the service."

While contrary to other sentiments of other users across other motor-hailing apps, users find the pricing of Angkas affordable most especially that the majority of their users are students.

A85 states that "Using Angkas is convenient and cost-effective, especially during rush hours."

One of the reasons for positive sentiments by Angkas is that they are one of the first motor-hailing apps to launch in Cebu making users loyal and have long-term satisfaction. A loyal user, A82 says that "I've been using Angkas since 2017 and I've never had any problems with their service!"

This continuous update coming from users' feedback aligns with the framework of the SERVQUAL model. The SERVQUAL model, developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, measures service quality based on five key dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Applying this to Angkas, the updates to its app reflect improvements across several of these dimensions including tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Enhancing the user interface such as their visual design, layout, and functionality improves the tangible aspect of the service—what users see and interact with. Additionally, by updating features for smoother bookings, payment options, and ride tracking shows Angkas' commitment to providing consistent and dependable service.

Moreover, by regularly refining the app based on user feedback demonstrates Angkas' agility in responding to customer needs promptly. With a more professional, user-friendly platform boosts users' confidence in the app's safety, efficiency, and legitimacy while by targeting the needs and preferences of younger users, Angkas shows it understands and values its users' specific expectations. Using the SERVQUAL model, the effectiveness of Angkas' app updates implies a strategic focus on service quality improvement. It suggests that Angkas is not just a transport provider but a user-centered service that prioritizes user satisfaction. An approach that helps build loyalty and trust, especially among the digitally native younger

Overall, Angkas receives a positive sentiment due to customer loyalty and consistent app update based on customer's feedback.

Maxim

Maxim's neutral sentiment score of 0.14 is the result of a balanced mixture of positive and negative sentiments, with both extremes appearing frequently in the dataset. This score does not imply that customers are indifferent or have no opinion, but rather that positive and negative perceptions coexist, effectively neutralizing each other. This balance is evident in the diverse set of customer feedback.

Many users express positive experiences, often praising driver behavior, reliability, or the cost of services. For example, M5 mentions "Very helpful app for deliveries, especially during challenging times" and M16 saying "App offers fair pricing but has issues with inaccurate pins and geotagging" are tagged with high positive scores. These comments reflect satisfaction with punctuality, affordability, and professionalism.

However, these positive remarks are counterbalanced by strong negative sentiments that focus primarily on driver behavior, booking reliability, and customer service. Statements like that of M25 saying "drivers keep canceling bookings due to low fare, causing delays" and M61 noting that "the driver was rude and unprofessional on the phone" carry strong negative sentiment tags. Such feedback reveals significant issues in operational consistency and communication, both of which are known to negatively influence perceived service quality and trust (Mai et al.).

Additionally, a number of entries are tagged as neutral, which typically reflect vague, factual, or mixed-opinion statements. For example M2 notes, "App offers cheap rates but has booking difficulties" or "Long wait for a rider, but fast delivery and receipt provided." neither praise nor criticize the service in a meaningful way. According to Liu (2012), neutral sentiments often arise from objective comments or when no strong emotion is conveyed. These neutral comments contribute to diluting the strength of either polarity, reinforcing the overall neutrality.

The neutral sentiment emerges not because the customers are indifferent, but because of high emotional polarity on both sides of the spectrum. The spreadsheet contains nearly equal proportions of very positive and very negative sentiments, which effectively cancel each other out. This phenomenon is observed in sentiment analysis literature, where texts with balanced emotional content across categories tend to be interpreted as neutral by automated sentiment classifiers (Hartmann et al.).

Moreover, some statements show conflicted sentiments, where both positive and negative elements appear in a single response. For instance, M55 states that, "Drivers are polite, but their helmets are unsanitary and have an unpleasant smell, which is a concern shared by others." This mixed feedback reflects what Iglesias and Moreno calls compound sentiment, where opposing sentiments are expressed simultaneously, often resulting in a net neutral sentiment assignment by classifiers.

In summary, Maxim commonly receives compound sentiments resulting from its neutrality as users praise the app for its affordability, friendly drivers, and overall convenience, while also criticizing persistent technical issues, limited features, and occasional policy or service shortcomings.

JoyRide

Joyride's neutral sentiment arises from the way users' comments mix praise and criticism. In examining the user statements, it is clear that many comments contain both positive and negative elements that roughly cancel out.

For example, J8 notes, "I like that I can book a car faster than the other app... But overall, it's convenient and it's great," praising the app's speed and convenience while suggesting room for improvement. Another comment from J13 says, "Overall App SuperB but needs additional improvement to Pin my Exact Location rather than typing the correct address but it is not the right location I've arrived or delivery of some of my items via Delivery Express, unlike other Apps, I can pin my own location, the rest, everything is ok." This user begins by highlighting friendly drivers, then adds a "however" clause to emphasize a usability issue. These examples illustrate how single comments often pair a compliment such as "great drivers" or "superb app" with a complaint, such as the app being difficult to navigate or lacking in features, leading to an overall neutral tone.

Other comments show this balancing more explicitly. J11 says, "I know safety is priority but how can you not consider women... heartbreaking this limits woman to take this mode of transpo." This statement starts by acknowledging the app's emphasis on safety but then criticizes a specific policy affecting women, introducing a tension between values and experience. J12's comment reads, "The service is great and way cheaper than other ride hailing apps... [missing map info]." It begins positively with terms like "great" and "cheaper," but then notes a shortcoming that directly impacts the usability of the service.

In contrast, a few comments are purely positive, such as those praising quick bookings or polite drivers, while others are overtly negative, like J4 stating, "This app's broken as hell." This contrast and frequent internal contradiction within single user comments reinforce the overall neutral sentiment, as positive and negative views are often presented side by side, effectively balancing each other out.

However, the majority include both favorable and critical remarks. As a result, no single polarity dominates. From a sentiment-analysis perspective, these mixed comments naturally yield a neutral score. In sentiment classification, text is typically labeled positive, negative, or neutral based on overall polarity. As Bing Liu explains, at the sentence level a piece of text is classified as positive, negative, or neutral, with "neutral" usually meaning no overall opinion or balanced sentiment (Liu).

In practice, many algorithms compute a numeric polarity score—often ranging between -1 and $+1$ —by summing positive and negative linguistic cues within a given statement. When these positive and negative expressions offset one another, the resulting score gravitates toward zero, indicating a neutral sentiment. Valdivia et al. (2017) explain that opinions expressing mixed or conflicting sentiments may be interpreted as neutral, especially when they convey both commendation and criticism within the same context. In a follow-up study, Valdivia et al. further emphasize that neutral reviews often carry an "equitable burden of positive and negative polarity," reinforcing the idea that neutrality in sentiment analysis does not necessarily reflect emotional absence, but rather a balance in opposing evaluations. This framework helps to explain Maxim's sentiment outcome: although users express emotional engagement, the frequent coexistence of approval and disapproval in individual statements causes the sentiment polarity to stabilize near zero, producing the observed neutral score.

This describes what is observed in the Joyride comments: multiple users combine praise, such as fast booking, friendly drivers, and lower fares, with complaints, including app glitches, missing features, and policy issues, often within the same sentence. Because each comment

frequently contains both encouraging and critical language, the aggregated sentiment averages out to approximately zero. In other words, positive expressions like “great service,” “superb,” and “thank you” are largely counterbalanced by negative expressions such as “broken,” “recklessly,” and “needs improvement,” resulting in a neutral overall tone. This balancing effect accounts for the sentiment score of 0.14, which is categorized as neutral. In sum, the Joyride feedback demonstrates mixed sentiments—comments that are neither overwhelmingly positive nor wholly negative. This aligns with the standard theory in sentiment analysis, where texts containing a balanced distribution of positive and negative language are interpreted as neutral.

All in all, JoyRide gets a neutral sentiment because user praise for fast booking, friendly drivers, and low fares are balanced by criticism of app glitches, missing features, and policy issues.

Move It

Move It receives a negative sentiment score of -0.40, which reflects the overall dissatisfaction expressed by users. This rating results primarily from a recurring pattern of frustration over technical issues, poor user experience, and service unreliability noted throughout the user comments.

A closer look at the feedback shows that users frequently point out app instability, a confusing or dysfunctional interface, and problems with booking or location accuracy.

For instance, MI2:

“I tried to make a booking and it just keeps on searching until I just cancelled it out. I’m pretty sure I click the X button and it was still searching then the next window was a driver arriving. The map was not being updated as well so I cannot monitor where the driver was. But this app has lots of potential. Hopefully, they invest to improve the UI of the app.”

This indicates persistent functionality issues that hinder basic app usage. MI3’s comment reads:

“I think they should fix the app, because i think the location of both parties are not accurate. It is a great option when considering its fare which is lower compared to other apps but i think conveniency when using this app is a meh. Hope they will fix the app because I can see potential in this as it is beginner friendly.”

This suggests dissatisfaction with the interface and navigability. These kinds of remarks reflect not just a single complaint, but an overarching theme of technical unreliability, which heavily influences the overall sentiment.

Additionally, the statement of MI6 mentioning “Let’s be honest the app’s interface and user experience are not good” underscores the negative perception of the platform’s usability. The use of the phrase “let’s be honest” emphasizes that the critique is not isolated but rather resonates with broader user sentiment. This comment, paired with others calling for app fixes or expressing booking difficulties, shows that technical flaws are not only common but critical enough to dominate user impressions.

According to Liu, negative sentiment often emerges when users perceive a failure in functionality, efficiency, or value delivery, especially in apps where performance directly affects service. This is supported by Valdivia et al., who explain that text expressing a majority of negative cues tends to skew overall sentiment scores downward, particularly when such cues dominate over any neutral or positive language. In Move It’s case, even neutral remarks—such

as users stating they “usually” book through the app’s queuing system—are outweighed by consistent grievances.

Moreover, none of the comments in the dataset provide strong or repeated positive expressions to offset the negativity. While neutral or slightly appreciative tones exist, they are limited and often embedded in complaints. The absence of strong praise for elements like driver behavior, pricing, or convenience—contrary to what was observed in the feedback for Maxim—further contributes to Move It's clearly negative classification.

In summary, Move It garners a negative sentiment score because the feedback centers overwhelmingly on technical problems, unfriendly user design, and difficulty in accessing core services like booking and navigation.

The sentiment analysis of the four motor-hailing apps can be meaningfully interpreted using the SERVQUAL model, which evaluates service quality based on five dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Parasuraman et al.).

Angkas receives a generally positive sentiment, largely attributed to its consistent reliability and responsiveness. Many users express loyalty toward the app, citing its quick service, reliable drivers, and the company's continued effort to update the app based on user feedback. This demonstrates strong responsiveness by addressing user concerns promptly and assurance, with riders feeling secure in the professionalism of drivers and system reliability. The emphasis on continuous improvement and customer-centric updates also reinforces Angkas’s high empathy and service reliability, which drive positive perceptions and long-term usage.

Additionally, Maxim and Joyride both register neutral sentiments, primarily due to a balance of positive and negative experiences in core SERVQUAL dimensions. Users often commend Maxim and Joyride for their affordability and polite or friendly drivers, aligning with the assurance and empathy dimensions of service quality. However, both apps are frequently criticized for technical issues such as difficulty with navigation or booking features, slow or inaccurate GPS, and occasional system glitches. These weaknesses reflect shortcomings in tangibles and reliability. Despite their strengths in cost-effectiveness and driver behavior, the frequent mention of these unresolved technical flaws prevents either app from earning distinctly positive sentiments, thus resulting in a neutral score.

Move It, on the other hand, receives a clearly negative sentiment score, as the feedback leans heavily toward user dissatisfaction with core service elements. Users commonly report difficulty accessing key features such as booking and navigation, and frustration with the app’s interface and overall usability. These complaints highlight deficiencies in tangibles and responsiveness such as poor app design and failure to resolve technical issues in a timely manner. Furthermore, the lack of user-centric adjustments or perceived support reflects weak empathy and reliability, reinforcing the overall negative perception. Compared to the other platforms, Move It appears to underperform across multiple SERVQUAL dimensions, which aligns with its negative sentiment score.

All in all, Angkas receives a positive sentiment, while Maxim and JoyRide are viewed neutrally, and Move It receives a negative sentiment.

Underlying Reasons for Utilization Analysis

This section discusses the underlying reasons for utilization of the motor-hailing apps by Cebuanos.

Table 4. Underlying Reasons for Utilization

Motor-hailing Apps	Reasons	Percentage	Rank
Angkas	Accessibility	24.0	1
	Routine Transportation	24.0	
	Positive Driver Interaction	24.0	
	Safety and Reliability	13.0	2
	Driver's Good Hygiene	5.5	3
	Expensive	5.5	
	Discounts and Marketing	4.0	4
Maxim	Routine Transportation	54.0	1
	Affordability	18.8	2
	Convenience	9.4	3
	Emergencies	7.0	4
	Availability of Drivers	3.5	5
	Variety of Services	3.5	
	Safety and Reliability	2.3	6
	Accessibility	1.0	7
Move It	Routine Transportation	51.8	1
	Convenience	14.8	2
	Affordability	8.6	3
	Positive Driver Interaction	6.1	4
	safety and Reliability	4.9	5
	Service Quality	4.9	
	Emergencies	3.7	6
	Limited Drivers	1.2	7
	Discounts and UX Design	1.2	
	Driver's Good Hygiene	1.2	
	Leisure and Travel	1.2	
JoyRide	-	-	-

Table 4 presents the underlying reasons why users prefer the different motor-hailing apps. The major motivations for Angkas are accessibility, routine transportation, and positive driver interaction, each at 24%, followed by safety and reliability at 13%. Maxim users primarily recognize routine transportation as their primary reason for using the app, with 54%, followed by affordability and convenience, with 18.8% and 9.4%, respectively. Move It users identify routine transportation as their most significant factor, with 51.8%, with convenience and affordability following, each accounting for 14.8% and 8.6%, respectively. Whereas JoyRide users do not provide any underlying reasons why they choose to utilize the app.

The utilization of Angkas is influenced by several underlying factors, including accessibility, routine transportation, positive driver interaction, safety and reliability, driver's hygiene, expensive pricing, and marketing strategies.

Accessibility emerged as the top reason for using Angkas. Respondents highlighted the convenience and availability of the service, which aligns with the 'perceived ease of use'

component of TAM, suggesting that users are more likely to adopt a user-friendly technology that requires minimal effort. In the context of Cebu's traffic conditions, the ability to quickly book a ride and navigate through congested areas makes Angkas a compelling option. This is further supported by UGT, which posits that individuals actively seek out media and services that fulfill specific needs, such as convenience and efficiency in transportation

Routine transportation is another factor influencing Angkas usage. Users reported relying on the service for their daily commutes, indicating a habitual use pattern. This behavior reflects the 'perceived usefulness' aspect of TAM, where users believe that the technology enhances their performance in daily tasks (Venkatesh & Davis). The STP Model also provides insight, as Angkas appears to target commuters who require reliable and consistent transportation, positioning itself as a dependable service for routine travel

Positive driver interaction significantly affects user satisfaction. Respondents noted that Angkas drivers are respectful, patient, and accommodating. For instance, R1 mentions that, "Angkas are safe and very reliable. Their drivers are very respectful." Such feedback aligns with the 'empathy' and 'assurance' dimensions of the SERVQUAL model, which assess the courtesy and ability of service providers to inspire trust and confidence.

Safety and reliability are paramount concerns for users. Respondents expressed feeling secure when using Angkas, with R9 stating, "I strongly prefer Angkas since I feel safe, especially riding going anywhere." This perception is crucial, considering the inherent risks associated with motorcycle transportation. The assurance dimension of the SERVQUAL model is relevant here, as it evaluates the competence and credibility of the service provider. Furthermore, safety and reliability have been identified as key factors influencing the adoption of motorcycle taxi services in urban areas (Gössling). Consumers are more likely to choose services that offer both perceived safety and consistent performance, particularly in densely populated regions like Cebu.

Another notable underlying reason for the utilization of Angkas is the driver's good hygiene, which contributes to riders' comfort and sense of care. Hygiene, although not always explicitly discussed in transportation literature, is a vital aspect of service quality, particularly in Southeast Asian contexts where weather and traffic conditions can exacerbate discomfort during commuting (Rayle et al.). Several respondents noted the cleanliness and readiness of Angkas riders, with R108 stating, "their helmets aren't in bad condition and they also have raincoats for back riders." This reflects an attentiveness to passenger needs and a standard of cleanliness that enhances the commuting experience, especially during the rainy season—a factor also highlighted by R61, who prefers using Angkas during such times. While R107 noted a concern about the smell of the helmet, the overall pattern suggests that Angkas riders are perceived as clean and hygienic, leading to a positive user experience. This finding aligns with the SERVQUAL model, which emphasizes tangibles, such as equipment condition and cleanliness, as a key dimension of service quality, ultimately influencing customer satisfaction. Pricing is another factor influencing user decisions. Some respondents perceive Angkas as more expensive compared to other options. R21 mentioned, "I don't really use Angkas that much because they have a higher rate due to having insurance for their passengers." This perception can be analyzed through the STP Model, where Angkas positions itself as a premium service offering added safety features, targeting users willing to pay more for enhanced security. However, price sensitivity remains a concern, and balancing cost with perceived value is crucial for user retention. Price sensitivity has been found to vary based on perceived safety benefits in ride-hailing services (Clewlow & Mishra). Emphasizing that

consumers are more willing to pay higher prices for services that offer greater safety and reliability.

Marketing strategies, including discounts and engaging social media content, also play a role in attracting users. R45 commented, "Their Facebook posts promoting their service are also so witty." This aligns with UGT, as users are drawn to services that not only fulfill functional needs but also provide entertainment and engagement. Effective marketing can enhance brand image and influence user preferences, especially among younger demographics. Creative and relatable marketing campaigns have been found to significantly impact user engagement and loyalty (Tussyadiah & Zach). This highlights the importance of emotional connections in fostering long-term customer relationships in the travel and transportation sector.

Maxim's services are chosen for the underlying factors such as routine transportation, affordability, convenience, emergencies, availability of drivers, variety of services, safety and reliability, and accessibility.

Maxim's superiority in routine transportation corresponds to Kotler's STP Model, focusing strategically on students and employees who need daily travel. Users often highlight its function in habitual travel, as seen in comments such as "Going to school, Running errands" R36–77. The Uses and Gratifications Theory accounts for this preference, as users value efficiency and dependability—qualities that are not typically found in regular transit. Evidence supports that ride-hailing mobile applications thrive in cities because of their flexibility (Rayle et al.), although Maxim's motorbike-based framework singularly overcomes Cebu's traffic gridlock.

Affordability is Maxim's differentiator, especially for students. R8 mentions that "Maxim is very student/budget friendly."

The SERVQUAL Model structures pricing as an essential element of service quality, and Maxim's competitive prices resonate in price-conscious markets. Comparative statements such as "Maxim is cheaper than Move It" R13 show active user cost comparisons, a trend that has been documented in developing economies (Shaheen et al.). But reduced costs can come at the cost of compromises; some comment "Move It is cheaper than maxim but some places not in there" R13, pointing out service gaps.

Users repeatedly commend Maxim for its ease of use: "I find Maxim very convenient" R25. TAM affirms the app's perceived ease of use, whilst the UGT highlights satisfaction from swift reservations. Convenience is, however, not a given; one user confesses, "I can't really tell other apps because I usually use Maxim" R22, implying minimal familiarity with others. Evidence suggests convenience predominates over expense (Alemi et al.), though issues such as "drivers don't actually pick up if I book to a far place" R20 suggest operational challenges. Maxim is also credited as an emergency substitute evident from R29-34 stating "Emergencies". The SERVQUAL Model connects this with reliability during crises, a role enhanced when public transport is inaccessible. Yet motorcycle-based emergencies are dangerous—a concession users make, as highlighted in "I haven't yet experienced any accidents" by R81. With that, studies affirm how ride-hailing satisfies essential gaps amidst transportation disruptions (Tirachini & Cats).

Moreover, Maxim's availability of drivers exhibits strengths and weaknesses based on users' experiences. Some users value the platform's geographical coverage, as R18 states "Maxim has a lot of drivers so I can easily find one when I'm in rush," which supports studies on the role of network density in ride-hailing apps' success (Clements & Kockelman, 2017). The strategic entry into delivery services by the company, as indicated by "Food/goods delivery" R83-84

and "I choose maxim because of faster delivery" by R85, attests to its embracing of multi-service approaches proven to enhance user retention (Shaheen et al.).

Maxim's safety and reliability scores high but comments suggest its complicated user dynamic. A user's remark (R81) perfectly describes this stress: "I have my fair share of negative experiences for both Moveit and Maxim, so I cannot give them a 5. But fortunately, I haven't yet experienced any accidents by frequently using motorcycle apps so it's a solid 4 for me." This illustrates the "safety paradox" in developing markets (Nguyen-Hoang and Yeung) in which safety in consumption is compromised for affordability. Critical flaws in driver vetting procedures that fall short of service are exposed by more concerning claims, such as R19's claim that "I switched to maxim when one of my friends encountered a pervert who almost assaulted her."

Compared to Angkas, Maxim is considered accessible or "Easy to use" only by one person: R1. This finding contradicts TAM for the app, suggesting interface challenges within the app. Studies stress intuitive design as critical for adoption (Hossain et al.)

The demand of ride-hailing services has given an essential urban mobility solution especially in fast-growing cities like Cebu, apps like Move It have gained traction among daily users for routine transportation, convenience, affordability, positive driver interaction, safety and reliability, service quality, emergency use, discounts and UX Design, Driver's Good Hygiene, Leisure and Travel.

Cebuanos primarily used the app for everyday trips, errands, or even emergencies, illustrating its critical function of providing a key urban mobility solution among users with limited access to transportation in urban cities. These usage types are aligned with the UGT theoretical concept which explains consumers select certain media and services to meet practical needs. In this instance, Move It is satisfying users' expectations regarding convenience, economic efficiency, and reliability. The rapid development of ride-hailing services is reshaping traditional modes of travel, with significant implications for urban mobility. For individuals with limited access to private vehicles or dependable public transportation, these services have been demonstrated to increase travel possibilities (Wadud). Users also identified multiple use cases.

R33 states that, "I primarily use the app for various purposes, including commuting to school, running errands (e.g., grocery, pharmacy), attending to emergencies, leisure or travel activities, and food or goods delivery."

The affordability and convenience of Move It differentiates it from other motor-hailing apps, positioning it as a balanced option for users who seek both cost-effectiveness and ease of use cited as the next most significant factors. The utilization of Move It can be interpreted through UGT, which posits that users actively select media or services based on specific needs and gratifications as defined by Katz, Blumler & Gurevitch. In this case, Cebuanos primarily use Move It to select services to satisfy their functional need for routine and reliable transportation. The theory also explains the app's appeal in terms of gratification of ease and gratification of economic efficiency. After the convenience of payment, waiting time is another common reason why customers choose to utilize e-hailing services. Factors such as travel speed and the distance between the vehicle's current location and the pickup point can influence the customer's waiting time. With that, the mode of payments like digital payments or by credit cards of digital payments and the ability to freely select their preferred e-hailing service further enhance user satisfaction (Niza et al.).

However, despite the fact that it is very useful and widely used, the user preference and satisfaction of Move It are, in fact, low, as indicated by its sentiment score of -0.40. Relative to other apps like Angkas, Maxim, and JoyRide. Moreover, a small yet notable percentage of users cited negative driver interaction and safety and reliability. For instance, R19 states that, "I tried it many times but I switched to maxim when one of my friends encountered a pervert who almost assaulted her."

R79 also mentions that, "For Move It, I rated four (4) because at times, some drivers are reckless and do not follow the designated pin locations. Aside from that, there are instances when they take an unusually long time to arrive, often going somewhere out of the way, which contributes to the delay."

This social and emotional feedback of the SERVQUAL model, where responsiveness and aspects of customer service quality influence user satisfaction and repeat usage. Such the attitudes of drivers can significantly affect the perceived service quality in urban areas (Manaois et al.). Additionally, the distrust in the platforms' built-in security measures, arguing that they expose users to malicious and criminal activities that jeopardize their safety while using ride-hailing services. Furthermore, driver behaviors that pose a danger to safety include careless driving, using a smartphone while operating a motor vehicle, and fee pricing policies that passengers perceive as opaque, which can result in conflicts between customers and ride-hailing drivers. (Acheampong).

Cebuanos appear to value platforms that are not only functional but also user-friendly and customer-centered. The presence of emergency use, UX design, discounts, driver hygiene, and leisure or travel hint at niche motivations as secondary gratifications. This tells that while the app is not yet perceived as a premium service, some users still see its value beyond their routine use. When compared to Angkas and Maxim. Move It appears to market itself that prioritizes user experience.

Nonetheless, in actual user experience, Move It appears to fall short in terms of customer responsiveness, reliability and security. R26 shares the following feedback:

"For Move It, I'll give a rating of three (3). First, sometimes during rush hour and heavy traffic, they don't accept ride requests. Second, when it's the rainy season, no one goes online. I understand that it's difficult to drive when it's raining because passengers can get wet, but some of them also don't provide raincoats. Third, based on my observation when I was at SM Seaside trying to book a Move It ride, there were a lot of drivers online, but no one accepted my request. So, I gave a ₱50 tip and that's when my ride was accepted."

With that, the security and attention to rider comfort also point up. R19 also states that, "I tried it many times but I switched to maxim when one of my friends encountered a pervert who almost assaulted her."

Factors influencing the continued usage of ride-hailing apps, demonstrates how Move It weakens the perceived importance of such concerns. For instance, consumer satisfaction and loyalty are significantly swayed by user experience (UX) design, security features such as emergency options, and incentives like discounts (Ofori et al.). In addition, features pertaining to leisure or travel and driver hygiene are examples of secondary gratifications that contribute to the service's total worth (Ofori et al.).

Thus, the utilization of Move It offers effective, convenient, and reasonably priced for everyday transportation needs. With experience and service quality, It is not preferred for many users due to concerns such as user experience and service quality. As urban transportation patterns change, Cebuanos are increasingly using the platform, which emphasizes the reliability and

user-centered services, focusing on the need of Move It to improve these areas to stay competitive in the motor-hailing sector.

Unfortunately, no data was recorded for the utilization of JoyRide as a motor-hailing app in the areas in Cebu. This shows that JoyRide may have limited usage or presence among commuters, unlike other apps like Angkas, Move It and Maxim.

Overall, the primary underlying reasons for Cebuanos use of Angkas, Maxim, and Move is because of their accessibility, routine transportation, affordability, convenience, and positive driver interaction.

Encountered Challenges Analysis

This section discusses the challenges encountered upon using the select motor-hailing apps.

Unfortunately, the survey's limitation in allowing respondents to select multiple motor-hailing apps resulted in generalized challenges applicable to all platforms instead of specific issues for each.

Table 5. Challenges Encountered

Challenges	Percentage	Rank
No challenges	19.0%	1
Limited Drivers During rush hours, bad weathers, and at night	14.5%	2
Rude Drivers	12.7%	3
Delayed Booking Confirmations	10.9%	4
Inaccurate Location Pinning	9.0%	5
Last-Minute Cancellations by Riders	8.1%	6
Reckless Drivers	5.4%	7
Poor Hygiene	4.5%	8
Late Driver Arrivals	3.6%	9
Lack of Real-Time Responsiveness	2.7%	10
Accidents	1.7%	11
Limited Discounts	1.7%	
App Crash	1.7%	
Slow or Inefficient Drivers	1.7%	
Limited Serviced Areas	0.9%	12
No-show Drivers	0.9%	

As presented in Table 5, a notable 19% of the respondents reported no issues, a good overall experience on Cebu's motor-hailing apps. Nevertheless, 81% still noted at least one issue, marking areas that need improvement. The top four issues were: 14.5% few drivers available during peak hours, inclement weather, or night, 12.7% rude drivers, 10.9% tardy booking confirmation delayed booking confirmations, and 9% incorrect location pinning.

These were closely followed by challenges such as inaccurate location pinning, last-minute cancellations, safety issues, and technical glitches. Collectively, these concerns highlight significant gaps in reliability, service consistency, and user experience factors essential to sustaining customer satisfaction and loyalty in digital transport services.

Despite the widespread acceptance of motor-hailing apps in Cebu for their accessibility and user-friendly interfaces, critical service limitations continue to hinder user satisfaction. These findings align with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), where perceived usefulness and ease of use influence adoption (Davis). R46 mentions that “the app is user-friendly, and even if I was in a place with an unstable signal, I was able to book a ride.” This highlights the platform’s technical convenience—a clear strength.

However, the most recurring concern was the lack of available drivers during peak hours, early mornings, and rainy weather, pointing to a reliability issue under the SERVQUAL model (Masud). One user explained, “It happens during rush hours... my bookings get cancelled maybe because my pickup point is far from the rider.”

According to Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), apps are used for the convenience they promise, and when that is disrupted, users are left dissatisfied and may seek alternatives.

Negative rider-driver interactions also emerged as a major issue, affecting empathy and assurance dimensions in SERVQUAL. Respondents reported rude behavior, delayed responses, or order rejections—factors that damage trust and discourage repeat usage. One respondent noted, “The rider got angry because I forgot to indicate a description... Sometimes riders didn’t accept the order immediately.” Such interactions, as Giddy points out, directly erode brand credibility in service platforms.

Other service challenges include frequent cancellations, often due to driver preferences for nearby or easier routes, which undermine both responsiveness and assurance. These inefficiencies, as noted by Tirachi, are often linked to weak algorithmic matching and regulatory gaps in Southeast Asian motor-hailing systems.

Safety is another critical concern. Users cited reckless driving, absence of helmets, and fears of accidents. These issues reflect poor adherence to the assurance factor and raise questions about rider protection. Although companies like Angkas claim to offer safety training and gear, Cebu Insights reports inconsistent enforcement, violating the broader aim of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 8 for safe and decent work conditions.

Finally, technical issues like GPS inaccuracies, app glitches, and delayed updates reduce user trust and platform reliability. A respondent shared, “Specifically for Move It... naa kos atbang kay mao akong gina-pin nga location niya si kuya rider na wrong siyag stop” (“Specifically for Move It... I’m across the street because that’s the location I pinned, but the rider stopped at the wrong place.”) According to Ruamchart, accurate navigation and stable app performance are essential for sustained satisfaction.

Some users experienced technical issues while using the apps, including crashes, slow loading, and inaccurate GPS pinning. These problems negatively impact perceived ease of use and usefulness—core components of the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis). As Ruamchart noted, app dependability and accurate location tracking are crucial for sustained user

satisfaction. When these functions fail, especially for new users, the experience becomes frustrating and discourages future use. Technical reliability remains a key factor in retaining user trust.

Aside from these technical concerns, several less frequent but notable issues emerged. These included last-minute cancellations (8.1%), reckless driving (5.4%), poor hygiene (4.5%), late arrivals (3.6%), and delayed booking responses (2.7%). A small number of users also mentioned accidents, app glitches, inefficient drivers, lack of promos (each at 1.7%), limited coverage, and no-show riders (each at 0.9%). While these were not the majority, they reflect ongoing weaknesses in driver behavior, system design, and service delivery. Even low-frequency issues can gradually erode platform credibility.

Overall, the majority of the users did not experience any challenges but the top challenges experienced by others include Limited Drivers During rush hours, bad weathers, and at night, rude drivers, delayed booking confirmations.

Enjoyed Features Analysis

This section discusses the features enjoyed by the users in using the select motor-hailings apps. The table presents varied features enjoyed by users of each motor-hailing app. For Angkas, users highlighted convenience and time-saving, safety, pricing, and rider attitude and availability. Maxim users prioritized convenience, pricing, and safety, while Move It users leaned toward convenience, pricing, and safety as well. JoyRide, however, lacked sufficient data for comparison, suggesting limited user engagement or awareness in the surveyed population.

Table 6. Enjoyed Features

Motor-hailing Apps	Features	Percentage	Rank
Angkas	Convenience and Time-Saving	33.33	1
	Safety	20.83	2
	Pricing	12.5	3
	Rider Attitude and Availability	12.5	
	Customer Service	8.33	4
	App Functionality	8.44	
	Discount and Marketing	4.17	5
Maxim	Convenience and Time-Saving	30.63	1
	Pricing	27.92	2
	Safety	16.21	3
	App Functionality	11.71	4
	Rider Attitude and Availability	6.3	5
	Customer Service	6.3	
	Discount and Marketing	0.9	6
Move It	Convenience and Time-Saving	26.95	1
	Pricing	25.21	2
	Safety	22.6	3
	App Functionality	11.3	4
	Customer Service	6.08	5
	Rider Attitude and Availability	4.34	6
	Discount and Marketing	3.47	7

JoyRide			
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For Angkas, convenience and time-saving dominated at 33.33%, reflecting its efficiency in meeting user needs. Safety followed at 20.83%, highlighting its reputation for secure rides, while pricing and rider attitude tied at 12.5%. Lower rankings for customer service at 8.33% and discounts at 4.17% suggest these are secondary concerns for Angkas users.

Time-saving features drive mobile service adoption. Time-conscious users highly value real-time tracking, cashless payments, and quick bookings, which save effort and reduce uncertainty compared to traditional transport (Kleijnen). Moreover, a study in *Case Studies on Transport Policy* emphasizes safety as a critical factor in ride-hailing adoption, particularly in emerging markets. It underscores that security enhancements are not just add-ons but essential drivers of market growth, with policy implications for urban mobility in developing economies (Acheampong).

A study titled “Linking Service Convenience to Satisfaction: Dimensions and Key Moderators” supports this, highlighting that service convenience—particularly in terms of search and transaction efficiency—is a strong driver of customer appeal by reducing time and effort (Benoit et al.). This suggests that positioning around convenience is especially effective for attracting busy professionals and high-income consumers in competitive service markets. Maxim users similarly prioritized convenience and time-saving at 30.63%, but pricing held greater weight at 27.92% compared to Angkas, indicating cost sensitivity. Safety remained important at 16.21%, while app functionality at 11.71% and rider attitude at 6.3% trailed. The minimal interest in discounts at 0.9% suggests Maxim’s user base values practicality over promotional incentives.

A study titled “Examining the Impact of Price Sensitivity on Customer Lifetime Value” reveals that price sensitivity significantly influences purchasing decisions, particularly in luxury markets where perceived quality and positioning outweigh pure cost considerations. The research identifies “quality positioning value” as a critical factor, showing that customers balance price against long-term value perceptions, with time and information availability further moderating these choices (Awaad et al.).

Move It mirrored the trend, with convenience and time-saving at 26.95% and pricing at 25.21% as top features. Safety ranked higher here at 22.6% than in Maxim, emphasizing its role in user satisfaction. App functionality at 11.3% and customer service at 6.08% were less critical, while discounts at 3.47% were the least prioritized, aligning with broader patterns.

Time-saving features significantly boost customer satisfaction and loyalty, confirming that convenience is a key driver in service adoption, especially relevant in motor-hailing apps. This aligns with user preferences across Angkas, Maxim, and Move It, where convenience ranked highest. Angkas users valued safety, while Maxim users placed more emphasis on pricing. App functionality also played a role in shaping customer satisfaction. JoyRide’s lack of data suggests low adoption or awareness, a gap that highlights the need for further investigation into market penetration or user perceptions (Seifert & Byun).

JoyRide’s lack of data precludes detailed analysis but implies limited adoption or visibility in Cebu. This gap warrants further investigation into market penetration or user perceptions.

All in all, the commonly enjoyed features for the ride-hailing apps are convenience and time-saving, pricing, and safety.

The study concludes that the assumption that the Cebuanos utilize the motor hailing apps out of urgency is proven to be true.

It is recommended that motor-hailing apps provide consistent updates based on user experiences, enhance technical features particularly real-time location tracking and localize marketing campaigns to boost app usability. Specific strategies include improving the user interface for Move It to streamline booking and navigation, implementing localized driver training programs for JoyRide to enhance customer service and safety, and introducing loyalty or rewards programs for Maxim to encourage user retention and frequent usage.

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